

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: THAPA****FIRST NAME: RAJAN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing Essay (EUCLID 2021, 10)
2. Some rule of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2021,11-14)
3. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-34)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
6. Chicago style and usage (EUCLID 2021, 44-57)
7. Sample response paper (EUCLID [2021](#), 66-71)

WRITING ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

People have their own choice of destiny in their academic field, and I am no different. Despite my desire to expand my academic career in climate change, it took me almost 3 years to identify EUCLID University, where I could pursue a doctorate (Ph.D.) in climate change and sustainability. My decision to apply for my Ph.D. was ultimately made after several visits to the website, reading the program brochure over ten times, and consulting with professors in Nepal and government agencies. I was confident and very excited from day one of my enrollment. In accordance with the instructions, I registered for ACA-401D in [Learning Management System \(LMS\)](#) portal and began studying.

I have now read the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack (period [one](#)), which has been revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma. I have also watched the tutorial video, which outlines citation style, headings, and paragraphs for writing the response paper. During my master's, I went through a similar course structure, but the content of this course is more comprehensive and has enabled me to gain a greater

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understanding of academic writing. Now I have a clear understanding that essay writing requires both critical and creative thinking.

In this response paper, I have tried to summarize my learning on sever major [concepts](#) of ACA-401/ACA-401D; [this](#) includes writing [essays](#), some [rules](#) of thumb for writing [papers](#), punctuations, American vs British language style, how to cite, style guide and sample response paper.

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2) WRITING ESSAY

In [Chapter I](#) of ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period I, the guidelines for essay writing are discussed. The chapter provides a brief overview of how academic essays are structured, tips for starting an essay, and finally, a guide to writing good essays.

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In practice, there are several kinds of essays, but academic essays usually include empirical evidence and provide answers to hypotheses based on the evidence (EUCLID 2021,7). When drafting an essay, it is crucial to start on time with a clear vision of what its purpose is and what the results will be. You can make this easier if you follow the basic steps in writing [an](#) essay. These steps will help you shape your [writing](#). After identifying or analyzing the purpose, it drives towards [the](#) identification of [the](#) research topic and collecting the information. While reading the documents, it is equally important for the writer to take notes and arrange them creatively. When I read [Chapter I](#), I noticed that with more accurate information, you will be able to craft a more creative essay.

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The next step is producing [the](#) first draft with adequate structure and framework. In a structured essay, there are three main sections: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. In the body of the essay, each paragraph should focus on one key point and provide supporting lines accordingly. When writing the sentence in academic writing, it also contains the references, so consistent reference throughout the paper is another crucial aspect.

In my research, I have found that if I keep the framework in mind, follow extensive review of the draft, proofread, check spelling, and punctuation, I will be able to produce good writing during my doctoral study in EUCLID. I also consider the [tutorial](#) videos to be [reference](#) material whenever I need a refresher.

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3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

In my academic and professional career, I have produced a number of publications, but writing long sentences is always a challenge for me, and I have been criticized many times for it. From this literature, I have noted that during the writing process, it should be made sure that the main point or main thesis is clearly stated from the beginning so that the essay flows logically. It is important that the paper not be generic in its presentation, but rather focus on a specific problem that it is trying to animate.

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When writing papers, if we simplify the sentences in an organized manner, assuming the reader's perspective, with evidence-based arguments, always helps to produce credible papers. It is also equally important to follow the rules of citation and referencing when citing texts taken from a variety of sources, writing a simple and catchy introduction, and performing multiple reviews and edits when writing papers.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Even though I finished my university degree in the English medium, I knew very little about American and British English. Usually, I use my laptop and [Personal Computer's \(PC\)](#) default English when drafting documents, but after reading this chapter, I understand these are two different versions, and we should use only one properly.

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Having read this literature, I now understand that in both languages, there would be different pronunciations, even if the spelling is the same, and [the same words](#) could have different meanings. It is, therefore, important to stick with one language throughout the essay, even though each language has its own history of [essence](#).

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5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is simply the use of information without crediting its source. According to EUCLID (2021, 34), plagiarism is “using a source of information without giving [credit](#) to the author of that information”. It could be said that plagiarism is unethical unless the author is given credit and the work is cited correctly. Especially in the age of Google, it is becoming easier to find information on the web, but we often don't take the time to give credit to the source or person who provided the information. My understanding from this chapter is that sharing knowledge is doable, but we should not forget to correctly cite the author or source of the information.

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From chapter IV of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period I, I learned that there are two ways to cite; in-text citations and a list of work cited. I have noticed that [giving credit to the author is the first rule when we use quotes, any data, chart, or figure](#). I am confident that this chapter will guide me in my future writing of multiple papers during my academic journey at EUCLID.

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6) STYLE GUIDE

According to EUCLID (2021, 41), style guide is [a means of documenting the approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need consistency](#). Consistency in writing style is important in all forms of writing, whether it is business writing, journalism, or commercial writing. There is evidence from the literature that punctuation and grammar are important, but style can influence the way we frame our writing, including fonts, layout, sentence length, structure, voice preferences, etc.

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The purpose of a style guide is to not only assist the writer, but also provide documentation of the audience's preferences. Thus, creativity in style and consistency throughout the document can increase the level of readers' or customers' satisfaction.

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While studying for my Ph.D. in EUCLID, I have noticed that I will have to submit several papers, and EUCLID has recommended the Chicago Rules, which is the first time I have heard of it. Since this Chicago Manual of Style has a very helpful website where I can find information and ask questions, I am very confident that following this style guide will result in an improved level of academic writing.

7) CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

As EUCLID has recommended the Chicago Rule in writing, I have learnt that this style will be more useful in writing term papers, thesis, and dissertations. The chapter in some ways can be considered a manual on Chicago Style: it briefly explains how to use abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, how to make words italic and mark quotations, and how to format pages.

The best part of this chapter is an example of every specific criterion. This section not only introduces the style, but also explains what to use, where and how the overall document should be structured.

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8) SAMPLE RESPONSE PAPER

The last chapter of ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period 1 focuses on sample corrections to papers. Using this sample response paper, you can learn the outline of writing a response paper in EUCLID. This chapter not only illustrates a sample of writing, but also provides information about how the paper will be reviewed by the instructor, how comments will be made, and some dos and don'ts of writing a response paper.

I now have a clear understanding of the proper guidelines and style needed when writing a response paper. The take-home message from this chapter is the more you practice and read related content, the better your writing products will be.

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9) CONCLUSION

My Ph.D. program in Climate Change and Sustainability begins with this session. Even though I regularly produce both academic and non-academic reports, when I started this session, I found myself with a limited understanding of different techniques of writing essays. My experience in this session taught me that you can improve your writing product by practicing and reading related content.

The beginner I am in many aspects and styles that this session highlighted, but I am confident that learning cannot be done in one go. There is only one way for me to make my journey [toward](#) completing my Ph.D. easier, and that is to read, reread, and rewrite.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, Director. 2021. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo video.

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